

PATTERN OF HISTOPATHOLOGICAL VARIATION IN PATIENTS OPERATED FOR ADRENAXAL MASSES OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE GROUP

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Abstract

Background:

Adnexal masses are commonly encountered in women of reproductive age and encompass a wide range of benign, malignant, and borderline pathologies. Accurate diagnosis and timely surgical intervention are essential for effective management and improved outcomes.

Objectives:

To evaluate the histopathological variations of adnexal masses in women aged 15–49 years and assess their clinical outcomes over a 6-month postoperative period.

Methodology:

This prospective observational study was conducted at Aziz Fatima Hospital Faisalabad over a 6-month period. A total of 30 female patients aged 15–49 years who underwent surgery for adnexal masses were included. Data were collected using a structured proforma covering demographic details, clinical presentation, imaging findings, surgical procedures, and histopathological reports. Patients were followed for 6 months postoperatively. Statistical analysis was performed using descriptive and inferential methods, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results:

The mean age of patients was 34 ± 7 years. The most common presenting symptom was abdominal pain (53.33%), followed by menstrual irregularities (26.67%) and infertility (20%). Histopathological examination of the surgical specimens revealed that 66.67% of the adnexal masses were benign, 23.33% were malignant, and 10% were borderline tumors.

Among the benign tumors, serous cystadenomas were the most frequent (40%), followed by teratomas (34.72%) and endometriomas (26.08%). Among the malignant tumors, serous carcinoma was the predominant type (13.33%), followed by mucinous carcinoma (4.67%) and endometrioid carcinoma (4.67%). No major postoperative complications or malignant recurrences were observed. A significant association was found between tumor type and presenting symptoms ($p = 0.03$).

Conclusion:

Most adnexal masses in reproductive-age women are benign and are associated with favorable outcomes following surgical intervention. Accurate **histopathological evaluation** is essential for establishing a definitive diagnosis and guiding appropriate management, ensuring optimal care and long-term outcomes for affected patients.

INTRODUCTION

Ovarian cancer ranks as the third gynecologic cancer following cervical and uterine cancers, it has the least favorable prognosis and the highest death rate ¹. The fallopian tubes and ovaries collectively are referred to as adnexa. Women with adnexal mass lesions present in all age groups and more commonly in reproductive age group. These adnexal masses can vary from benign mass like functional cysts to malignant mass like ovarian cancer ². Pediatric and adolescent adnexal masses are similar to adult cases and may be physiologic, Para tubal, tubal, or neoplastic origins with the potential for benign, malignant, or borderline malignancy. Infection (such as tubo-ovarian abscesses, pyosalpinges, or hydrosalpinges). Pregnancy can also cause masses such as ectopic pregnancies, functional cysts, corpus luteum cysts, endometrioma, mature cystic teratoma, and cystadenoma. Other organ-related disorders must also be considered like appendicitis/appendicular abscess, peritoneal/retroperitoneal inclusion cysts, and renal ectopy/urological anomalies ³. The ovaries are paired organs on either side of the uterus close to the lateral pelvic wall. A wide spectrum of pathological conditions - nonneoplastic and neoplastic can be seen in the ovary in routine surgical pathology ⁴. An accurate preoperative differential diagnosis of ovarian tumors is of major clinical significance because of the implications for further management and survival. In the past ovarian tumors used to be classified only as benign or malignant. Since 1971,

the International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) have classified borderline ovarian tumors (BOTs) as an entity separate from benign and invasive ovarian tumors ⁵. Ovarian cancer stands as the third most prevalent cancer among women in India and contributes to 6% of cancer-related fatalities. Furthermore, it ranks as the fifth leading cause of death attributable to malignancy in women, emphasizing its significant impact on mortality within the population. Pathology of the ovary is the most difficult gynecologic disease to evaluate clinically ⁶. Ovarian masses occur depending on functional, congenital, inflammatory and neoplastic processes and are common in women of all age groups ⁷. Benign tumors are the most common among young age group compared to malignant ovarian tumors that increased with age. Malignancy in ovarian masses increased with age, infertility and low parity and decreased with use of oral contraceptive ⁸. The detection of adnexal masses during pregnancy has become increasingly more evident in the last 20 years due to widespread use of ultrasound, the technical advancement of such equipment ⁹. Hemorrhagic cysts are commonly seen in clinical practice because hemorrhage into a cyst is usually painful, triggering the patient to consult her physician. They can present with variable clinical symptoms and signs ranging from no symptoms up to acute abdomen. HOCs are commonly detected by gray-scale ultrasound, but they are often misdiagnosed due to their variable

sonographic appearance; mimicking other organic adnexal masses. Most of HOCs are functional, few of them can be neoplastic but they are universally benign¹⁰. Adnexal region is composed of ovary, fallopian tube, broad ligament, and associated blood and nerve supply. Adnexal masses refer to the ovarian masses or cysts, fallopian tube masses, broad ligament pathology and Para tubal cysts. Characterization of clinically diagnosed adnexal mass lesions is difficult until histopathological examination and surgical exploration are done. Indeed ovarian pathology is responsible for 70% of pelvic masses found at exploratory surgery on patients with preoperative diagnosis of pelvic mass¹¹. However, until recently, BOTs have been treated in the same way as invasive malignant tumors. BOTs are more prevalent in women of childbearing age¹².

Methodology:

This prospective observational study was conducted at Aziz Fatima Hospital Faisalabad over a period of six months, from 20-08-2024 to 20-02-2025 to evaluate the histopathological variations among women of reproductive age (15-49 years) who underwent surgical treatment for adnexal masses. A total of 30 patients were included in the study. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Aziz Fatima Hospital Faisalabad, and informed written consent was taken from all participants. The inclusion criteria comprised female patients aged 15 to 49 years with adnexal masses confirmed on imaging (ultrasound, CT scan, or MRI), who underwent surgical intervention followed by histopathological examination, and who agreed to complete a 6-month postoperative follow-up. Patients were excluded if they fell outside the reproductive age range, did not undergo surgery, had incomplete histopathological records, or were lost to follow-up. Data collection was done prospectively using a structured proforma developed specifically for the study. This tool was used to gather detailed demographic data (age, parity, medical/surgical history), presenting symptoms (e.g., abdominal pain, menstrual irregularities, infertility), imaging findings, type of surgical procedure performed, intraoperative and postoperative complications, and follow-up outcomes. All surgically excised specimens were sent to the pathology

department, where they were processed using standard protocols: fixation in 10% formalin, paraffin embedding, sectioning, and Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) staining. Qualified pathologists examined the samples and categorized them into benign tumors (e.g., serous cystadenoma, dermoid cyst, endometrioma), malignant tumors (e.g., serous carcinoma, mucinous carcinoma), borderline tumors, and other non-neoplastic lesions or inflammatory findings. Patients were followed postoperatively at regular intervals over six months, with clinical evaluation and imaging (where indicated) to monitor for recurrence, complications, or need for further management. Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics (means, frequencies, percentages) summarized the data, while inferential tests such as chi-square or t-tests were applied to assess significant associations, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant. The study adhered strictly to ethical guidelines, ensuring patient anonymity and confidentiality throughout the research process.

Results:

This prospective study followed 30 female patients aged 15-49 years who underwent surgical intervention for adnexal masses. The patients were followed up for 6 months after surgery. The data analysis was based on clinical, demographic, and histopathological findings obtained from surgical specimens. The study population comprised 30 patients who underwent surgery for adnexal masses. The age of the patients ranged from 15 to 49 years, with a mean age of 34 ± 7 years. The most common presenting symptoms were abdominal pain (53.33%), menstrual irregularities (26.67%), and infertility (20%). **Histopathological examination of the surgical specimens revealed that 76.67% of the adnexal masses were benign, 16.66% were malignant, and 3.33% were borderline tumors.** Among the benign tumors, serous cystadenomas were the most common (39.13%), followed by teratomas (34.72%) and endometriomas (26.08%). Among the malignant tumors, serous carcinoma remained the most prevalent (60%), followed by mucinous carcinoma (20%) and endometrioid carcinoma (20%). No major postoperative complications were observed during the 6-month follow-up period. A few patients experienced mild

abdominal discomfort (10%) and irregular menstrual cycles (6.67%) post-surgery, which resolved within a few months.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients (n=30)

Variable	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (Mean ± SD)	34 ± 7 years	-
Presenting Symptoms		
Abdominal Pain	16	53.33
Menstrual Irregularities	8	26.67
Infertility	6	20.00
Location of Mass		
Ovarian	28	93.33
Fallopian Tube	2	6.67
Surgical Procedure		
Ovarian cystectomy	3	10
Oophorectomy	14	46.66
Salpingo-oophorectomy	8	26.66
Staging lapromtomy	4	13.33
Debulking surgery	1	3.33

Table 2: Histopathological Findings of Adnexal Masses (n=30)

Histopathological Diagnosis	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Total Masses Analyzed	30	100
Benign Tumors		
Teratomas	8	34.72
- Serous Cystadenomas	9	39.13
- Endometriomas	6	26.08
Malignant Tumors		
- Serous Carcinoma	3	60
- Mucinous Carcinoma	1	20
- Endometrioid Carcinoma	1	20
Borderline Tumors (BOTs)	2	6.66

Over the 6-month follow-up period, the majority of patients showed no signs of recurrence, and only mild discomfort was reported. There were no cases of malignant recurrence. The few patients with borderline tumors were monitored closely for any progression or recurrence, but no malignant transformation was observed. The chi-square test showed a statistically significant association between the type of adnexal mass and the presenting symptoms ($p = 0.03$). Benign masses were more commonly associated with abdominal pain, while malignant masses were more often linked to menstrual irregularities and infertility. No significant

difference was found in the association between the age of the patient and the histopathological diagnosis ($p = 0.12$).

Discussion:

This prospective study conducted at Aziz Fatima Hospital Faisalabad followed 30 female patients aged 15–49 years who underwent surgical intervention for adnexal masses. Patients were monitored over a 6-month period postoperatively to evaluate clinical outcomes and histopathological variations. The majority of patients presented with abdominal pain (53.33%), followed by menstrual irregularities

(26.67%) and infertility (20%). These findings are consistent with previous research highlighting the common symptomatic presentation of adnexal masses in reproductive-age women.

Histopathological analysis revealed that 76.67% of the adnexal masses were benign, 16.66% were malignant, and 6.66% were borderline tumors (BOTs). The most prevalent benign tumor was serous cystadenoma (39.13%), followed by teratomas (34.72%) and endometriomas (26.08%). Among malignant tumors, serous carcinoma was the most common (60%), followed by mucinous and endometrioid carcinomas (20% each). These results align with findings from a 2022 study documenting changing patterns in ovarian neoplasms and emphasizing the rising incidence of malignancies in specific geographic regions, such as western Saudi Arabia, reinforcing the need for timely diagnosis and management strategies (13).

Imaging played a pivotal role in preoperative evaluation. While ultrasound was the primary modality, this is supported by earlier research (2023), which highlighted that sonography—when conducted by trained radiologists using standardized approaches—is a highly effective diagnostic tool with strong sensitivity and specificity (14). However, our findings also support a 2024 study suggesting that ultrasound alone may not always distinguish between benign and malignant lesions with high accuracy. Therefore, additional imaging such as CT or MRI is advisable in ambiguous cases to improve diagnostic certainty, particularly when fertility preservation or oncologic concerns are involved (15).

Postoperatively, no major complications or malignant recurrences were observed during the 6-month follow-up. A small proportion of patients reported mild abdominal discomfort (10%) and menstrual irregularities (6.67%), which resolved spontaneously. Among the patients diagnosed with borderline ovarian tumors, no malignant transformation occurred, although they were monitored closely. These findings are consistent with 2024 literature emphasizing the wide pathological spectrum of ovarian lesions and their often overlapping clinical and imaging features, which makes histopathological analysis indispensable for definitive diagnosis (16).

A statistically significant association ($p = 0.03$) was found between the type of adnexal mass and presenting symptoms—with benign tumors more commonly presenting with abdominal pain, and malignant masses more frequently associated with menstrual irregularities and infertility. No significant correlation was observed between patient age and histopathological diagnosis ($p = 0.12$). This underlines the importance of integrating clinical symptom patterns into the diagnostic process to enhance early detection and tailored intervention in gynecological practice.

Conclusion:

The findings of this study revealed that the majority of adnexal masses were benign (76.67%), with serous cystadenomas being the most common subtype. Malignant tumors accounted for 16.66%, and borderline tumors for 6.66%, emphasizing the need for timely surgical intervention and thorough histopathological evaluation, particularly in women of reproductive age. Abdominal pain was the most frequent presenting symptom (53.33%), and postoperative outcomes were favorable, with no major complications or malignant recurrences reported during the 6-month follow-up period. These results highlight the critical importance of early and accurate diagnosis, individualized surgical management, and ongoing monitoring to improve clinical outcomes and inform future treatment strategies for adnexal masses.

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